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**Titel deutsch: Untersuchungen zum formschlüssigen Fügen von Eckbereichen
mithilfe der Inkrementellen Blechumformung**

Titel englisch: Investigations into the form-fit joining of corner sections by means of
incremental sheet forming

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this work to:

My beloved mother, Nadia, who passed away before I began my degree. May Allah bless her soul and reunite us with her in Paradise among those upon whom Allah has bestowed His favor: the prophets, the steadfast affirmers of truth, the martyrs, and the righteous. And excellent are those as companions.

My father, Ismail, whose unwavering support and prayers have been the backbone of my journey.

My brothers, Mahmoud and Mohammad, and their families, whose guidance and constant support have shaped my perseverance.

My sisters, Manal, Mais, Shatha, and Omaima, and their respective husbands and families, whose love and encouragement have been a great source of strength.

And my friends, who have stood by me through both the good and the difficult times.

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II List of Symbols and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ISF	Incremental Sheet Forming
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
3D	Three Dimensional
SPIF	Single-Point Incremental Forming
TPIF	Two-Point Incremental Forming
NC	Numerical Control
CAM	Computer Aided Manufacturing
CAD	Computer Aided Designing
DSIF	Double-Sided Incremental Forming

1 Introduction

In the field of modern manufacturing, scientific and technological innovations are increasingly oriented towards sustainable and efficient solutions. Metals continue to play a crucial role in this development, with widespread use across sectors such as the automotive industry, aerospace industry and consumer products. The advancement of metal forming techniques remains an essential driver for enabling flexible production processes that meet growing demands for customization, performance, and cost efficiency.

Among the various metal forming technologies, incremental sheet forming (ISF) has emerged as a highly flexible and cost-effective alternative, especially for small batch production and prototyping applications.

One significant application of sheet metal forming is hemming, which serves as a widely used joining technique for sheet metal assembly. Corner hemming involves additional complexity due to the presence of sharp radii or the change in radius value in general. Wrinkling and dimensional inaccuracies are among the issues encountered in corner hemming. These conditions make the forming process more demanding, requiring careful control of process parameters to address the associated challenges. Conventional hemming methods often face difficulties with complex shapes or small radii corners, where defects like wrinkling and geometrical inaccuracies commonly occur. For this reason, ISF has been adopted as a more flexible approach.

To successfully achieve reliable hemming at corners, this work integrates multiple sequential forming stages, including flanging, pre-hemming, and final hemming operations. The main objective of this study is to systematically investigate corner hemming by means of ISF, focusing on developing optimized process strategies for the flanging, pre-hemming, and hemming stages. Particular emphasis is placed on flange relief design and toolpath strategy development.

This investigation includes a comparative evaluation of different flange relief geometries, analysis on the effect of material removal areas, and the influence of pre-hemming strategies on the overall process performance. As no prior studies specifically address corner hemming using ISF, this work contributes to expanding the current state of knowledge in this area.

The experimental framework for this study involves the integration of a complete process chain, beginning with flanging, followed by pre-hemming, and concluding with final hemming. The forming operations are executed using a CNC system with general and customized ISF tools, and the produced geometries are analysed through optical 3D scanning measurements to assess dimensional accuracy.

Through this approach, the study aims to generate a deeper understanding of the process behaviour and the influence of key parameters. Ultimately, contributing valuable insights that support further development and industrial application of ISF for corner hemming tasks.

2 State of the Art

This chapter provides an overview of incremental sheet forming (ISF) and its related processes like flanging and hemming processes. The chapter begins with a general introduction to ISF, including its main classifications and the key influencing parameters. The latter sections discuss the flanging process and the hemming process including geometries and defects, with extra attention to shrink (convex) flanging and hemming cases.

This chapter sets the foundation for understanding the background and context of the experimental work conducted in this thesis.

2.1 Introduction to Incremental Sheet Forming (ISF)

The increasing demand for flexible manufacturing methods has led to a wave of research in order to discover new techniques over the past few decades. Incremental sheet forming has been considered one of the most promising techniques in terms of flexibility, cost effectiveness and rapid prototyping of samples and small batches production.

The name incremental forming is used for a variety of processes, all characterized by the fact that at any time only a small part of the product is actually being formed, and that the area of local deformation is moving over the entire product [Emm10]. ISF is basically a flexible sheet forming process where the forming tool deforms the sheet metal incrementally to a desired geometry.

The development of incremental sheet forming can be divided into three key periods, as summarized by a review paper by Emmens et al. The first period, up to 1996, represents the early history of ISF. During this time, patents were issued for processes that align with the ISF concept, specifically single point incremental forming (SPIF), but these did not lead to the modern processes seen today. The second period, from 1993 to 2000, saw significant progress in ISF, with the introduction of new variants like two point incremental forming (TPIF). Though developments and patent activity were largely confined to the Far East, particularly in Japan. The third period, from 2000 onwards, marked a shift towards increased research and patent activity in western countries, solidifying ISF as a viable and evolving manufacturing method globally.

ISF offers a solution to the problems and limitations caused by traditional sheet metal forming processes such as the high cost of tooling design and manufacture. ISF process allows the option of producing complex sheet components without the need for expensive dies or special tools, which makes it very suitable for industries requiring fast prototyping and small-scale production [Ami14].

However, ISF requires longer processing time compared to traditional sheet forming methods such as deep drawing which is basically capable of producing a part within a second or less. The ISF process is usually held at room temperature and requires a CNC machine, a basic support to hold the sheet metal (blank) in place, as well as a spherical tip tool [Pop24].

2.2 Dieless NC Forming

ISF and dieless NC forming are considered to be flexible forming techniques. A key difference between them lies in the use of dies. Dieless NC forming is conducted without any dies while ISF can incorporate partial or full dies.

The dieless NC forming was developed in Japan and it is considered to be an alternative production technique to traditional stamping methods. And it was meant to prototype stampings and create panels in small quantities. In this dieless forming method, an incremental forming procedure is used to shape the sheet metal to three dimensions. It is noticeable that the forming forces are generally decreased due to the incremental forming process [Ami14].

In the early 1990s, Polytechnic University professor Matsubara established the fundamental principle of dieless formation. The forming machine and technological development began in 1996. In that year, AMINO Corporation created the first machine prototype shown in Figure 2.1. In 1998, AMINO also created the dieless forming CAM (Computer-Aided Manufacturing) program. AMINO company began supplying specialist equipment to industries worldwide in 2002 [Ami14].

The machine is designed in a way that the tool operates in the Z direction, the workholder operates in X and Y directions. The workholder is also capable of compensating the vertical movement of the tool in the Z direction if needed. The CAD (Computer Aided Designing) mathematical credentials needs to be converted to NC (Numerical Control) through CAM programs. Eventually, this will provide a g-code that could be downloaded into the machine system. Then the sheet is gradually formed from the top to the bottom as the tool steps vertically [Ami14].

A wide range of materials can be formed into complicated shapes using this numerically controlled incremental forming, and it helped in decreasing the costs of traditional tooling as well as the lead time required. Amino Corporation is the most noticeable industrial company using and developing this process method [Ami14].

Figure 2.1 The first prototype machine [Ami14].

The basic idea of incremental forming is simple: a hemispherical or a parabolic punch deforms the sheet metal blank by following a predetermined toolpath. Which leads to producing a part with a complicated shape as shown in Figure 2.2. As a result, the sheet gradually undergoes plastic deformation until the part's final shape is obtained [Maq18].

Figure 2.2 Principle of incremental forming [Pop24].

2.3 Classification of the Incremental Forming Process

Recent studies in the subject have shown a number of ways to enhance and optimize the processes used for incremental sheet forming. There are many different configurations of the incremental forming process. Figure 2.3 outlines the primary classification criteria for the incremental forming process [Pop24].

Figure 2.3 Classifications of incremental forming process [Pop24]

The three most common variations of the ISF process based on forming tools contact points can be classified as single point incremental forming (SPIF), double sided incremental form-

ing (DSIF) and the two points incremental forming (TPIF). The goal of these variations is basically to increase the parts dimensional and shape precision [Pop24]. The next sections address these process variations, exploring their specific characteristics and differences.

2.3.1 Single Point Incremental Forming (SPIF)

Single point incremental forming is considered to be the most straightforward and cost-effective variation of ISF. This process is basically consisting of a single hemispherical shaped tool which deforms the sheet metal blank incrementally and moves in a predefined toolpath. As for fixing, the blank is fixed from all edges as shown in Figure 2.4.

This process variation is ideal for the production of small quantities and prototyping samples. It is also very easy to set up and very flexible compared to the other variations of ISF. However, the dimensional accuracy is relatively low compared to the other variations of ISF, for instance the angles formed in SPIF have lower accuracy [Pop24].

Figure 2.4 Principle of SPIF process [Pop24].

In order to increase the parts quality in SPIF, some parameters could be optimized such as the tool diameter, vertical step size and toolpath. This optimization is highly recommended in order to obtain the highest production quality possible [Maq18]. The parameters will be discussed in more detail in section 2.4.

Among the variations of ISF techniques, SPIF is considered to be the most widely used one [Pop24]. This is why its advantages and disadvantages will be discussed in the following sections.

Advantages of the SPIF

The advantages of SPIF, as identified by [Jad03] and [Jes05], include its ability to increase material formability and reduce forming forces due to the incremental nature of the process. The method significantly reduces production costs by eliminating the need for custom dies and by utilizing low-cost punches. Furthermore, design modifications can be implemented quickly and easily, as changes to the product can be made by simply adjusting the toolpaths. This flexibility allows for the production of a wide range of products with varying forms and sizes. The process is also compatible with commonly available industrial robots and three-axis CNC machines, making it accessible for many manufacturing settings. Another key advantage is the short lead time in prototype manufacturing, unlike traditional plastic deformation processes that can take longer time periods, prototypes can be produced within a few hours using SPIF, as highlighted by [Chu15].

Disadvantages of the SPIF

Despite its benefits, SPIF also presents several limitations as noted by [Jes05]. It is not suitable for mass production due to its inefficiency in handling large quantities. The forming process takes longer than conventional sheet forming methods such as deep drawing. Additionally, the technique can lead to springback, which results from residual stresses remaining after the forming process. A further disadvantage is the reduced geometrical accuracy of the final parts, particularly at the edges.

2.3.2 Double Sided Incremental Forming (DSIF)

The double sided incremental forming (DSIF) process represents a significant evolution in the field of incremental forming. It was first proposed in 2007 by Meier and his collaborators during their research on incremental sheet forming. Their goal was to balance the forces applied to the sheet during the ISF process as well as enhancing the materials deformability and increasing the precision of the parts [Mei07].

Similar to SPIF, a punch is used in this operation to deform the sheet blank, and the difference is the use of a counterpunch. This counterpunch is utilized to support the sheet blank and therefore providing more stability to the sheet during the forming process. The two punches designated toolpaths are synchronized together considering the thickness of the sheet and the wall angle. Figure 2.5 illustrates the principle of DSIF [Mei07] [Pop24].

Figure 2.5 Principle of DSIF process [Pop24].

This process variation demonstrated that the parts manufactured using the DSIF method are significantly more precise than those made using the SPIF process, and the distribution of material thickness is considerably more uniform. Additionally, a decrease in the forming forces was noticed as well as an increase in the surface quality. [Mei11]

The DSIF process is generally ideal for manufacturing parts requiring high degree of precision such as medical devices and aerospace components. This is due to its enhanced accuracy and the higher quality of surface finish. However, the complicated tooling and synchronizing could stand as a challenge to this process [Pop24].

2.3.3 Two Points Incremental Forming (TPIF)

Similar to the previous techniques, the two points incremental forming process involves fixing the sheet metal blank between the blank holder and the die. The sheet is deformed from top to bottom as the punch moves along the toolpath and steps vertically. The die configuration could be partial die, full positive or full negative as shown in Figure 2.6 [Pop24]. The important features of the desired shape are supported by the active die in order to enhance the precision of the final product [Jur06].

Figure 2.6 Principle of TPIF process [Pop24].

This ISF variation increases the precision and the surface quality of the produced pieces because the active die supports the sheet while the punch deforms it [Jes05]. Despite the significant advantages and enhancements in final product quality that this approach offers. This approach is considered to be more expensive than SPIF due to the need of an active die, and therefore, designing and manufacturing of the die itself. It is also considered to be less flexible for the exact same reason [Sil08].

2.4 Influencing Parameters for ISF

2.4.1 Tool Diameter

Although there is no official standardization for incremental forming tools, general purpose tools like hemispherical head tools or rollers are commonly used and can be adapted to suit the requirements of different geometries. However, for precise or specialized applications, custom tool designs may be necessary to ensure optimal forming results.

The main parameter considering the hemispherical forming tool is the diameter of the tool. In order to produce pieces with the right form and shape, and to reduce the amount of defects, selecting the appropriate tool diameter is crucial [Pop24].

To understand the effect of the tool diameter on the process, many studies have investigated this topic, with most using punches ranging from 4 mm to 50 mm in diameter [Pop24].

In a research conducted by Ham et al., the forming angle was recognized as a direct measure of material formability in incremental sheet forming. Their experiments utilized AA3003-O aluminium and explored how tool size (4.7625 mm and 12.7 mm), step size (0.0508 mm, 0.127 mm, and 0.254 mm), and material thickness (0.81 mm, 1.2 mm, and 2.1 mm) influenced the maximum forming angle [Ham06].

It was observed that the step size had little effect on the maximum forming angle. However, the material thickness, tool size, and their interaction demonstrated a significant influence on the maximum forming angle. Notably, the experiments showed that the maximum forming angle decreased with increasing tool diameter [Ham06].

Other researches also showed that the stress concentration on the material increased with decreasing the punch diameter, and localizing the material necking became easier using bigger punch diameter [Sil11].

The impact of tool diameter on material formability in incremental sheet forming is a topic of considerable debate within the field. The literature shows that the tool diameter has a direct influence on the material formability during incremental sheet forming.

Most studies indicate that reducing the tool diameter tends to increase material formability. For example, Ham et al. [Ham06] [Ham07], Martins et al. [Mar09], and Petek et al. [Pet09] highlight this trend, observing that smaller punch diameters enhance the materials deformability. Materials investigated in these studies include a variety of aluminium alloys (AA3003-O, AA6451, AA5182 and AA5754), several polymers (POM, PE, PA, PVC, PC), and DC05 steel [Pop24].

Conversely, other studies suggest that increasing the tool diameter can also improve material formability. Strano et al. [Str05], Frazen et al. [Fra09], and Golabi et al. [Gol14] reported improved formability with larger tool diameters. Materials investigated in these studies were AA1050-O aluminium alloy, PVC and SS304 stainless steel [Pop24].

Apart from this debate, using a relatively small tool diameter can be critical for the process because of the higher stress concentration at the contact point between the tool and the sheet. While smaller tool diameters can improve geometric accuracy, for example the maximum forming angle. They also increase the risk of material thinning and cracking defects [Pop24].

Other tool customizations have also been explored. For example, some studies used punches with a rotating ball tip instead of a fixed one. This modification changes the friction condition from sliding to rolling friction. Using the rotating ball tool has been shown to improve material deformability and enhance the surface roughness characteristics [Kim02].

2.4.2 Lubrications

In the incremental sheet forming process, the contact area between the blank and the punch is quite narrow. This results in high contact pressure and elevated frictional resistance. Since both deformability and surface quality are significantly influenced by this friction, managing it is essential for delivering products with good surface quality [Pop24].

Lubricants are used to minimize the effect of friction between the punch and the blank, therefore increasing the surface quality [Pop24]. As well as increasing the service life of the components and the punch [Lee02]. Figure 2.7 shows a comparison between parts formed with and without lubricants [Pop24]. It can be seen that Figure 2.7(a) exhibits a smoother and more uniform surface with fine, regular tool marks. In contrast, Figure 2.7(b) shows a part formed without lubrication, displaying a rough, irregular surface texture with visible scratches and material accumulations.

Figure 2.7 Surface quality of parts forms with ISF process (a) with lubricant and (b) without lubricant [Pop24].

2.4.3 Other Influencing Parameters

Apart from the previously discussed parameters, there are several other parameters that also play a crucial role in the ISF process. These will only be addressed briefly in the following sections.

Feed rate

The feed rate is the speed of the tool when travelling across the blank and it is measured in mm/min. increasing the feed rate can speed up the forming process which will make the process more efficient, but it could lead to possibility of increasing the surface roughness. The feed rate value should be suitably selected to provide a balance between time efficiency and component surface quality. The feed rate value typically varies from 300 mm/min up to 2000 mm/min [Pop24].

Vertical step size

The vertical step size is considered to be the depth which the tool travels vertically on the blank per pass in order to deform it, and it is measured in mm. Smaller step sizes like 0.2 mm achieves greater surface smoothness and less springback, while larger step sizes like 1.0 mm can increase the forming process speed and therefore, reduce the process time, but on the expense of dimensional accuracy [Pop24]. Figure 2.8 shows the vertical step size by means of incremental sheet forming [Tis12].

Figure 2.8 The vertical step size by means of incremental sheet forming [Tis12]

Toolpath

Toolpath is known to be the route that the punch follows over the blank when deforming it. The geometrical accuracy, surface quality, material deformability and the residual stresses are all significantly impacted by the toolpath selection [Pop24]. Figure 2.9 shows different toolpaths in ISF [Sch20].

Figure 2.9 Different toolpaths in ISF [Sch20]

2.5 Flanging Process

Flanging is a sheet metal forming technique based on bending the sheet metal over a die to produce a flanged part. It is generally used in automobile and aircraft industries. Flanging can be formed using different forming techniques such as conventional stamping, incremental forming, rubber forming, fluid forming and electromagnetic forming [Dew23].

Straight flange parts are produced by bending the sheet metal over a flat die. While stretch and shrink flanges are created by bending the sheet over concave and convex dies. Another type of flanging involves forming a sheet with a pre-cut hole until it reaches a specific height, creating a hole-flange [Ans99].

All flanging processes are performed using a die, punch, blank holder and the blank. Figure 2.10 illustrates the basic process of flanging by means of incremental sheet forming [Dew23].

Figure 2.10 Flanging process by means of incremental sheet forming [Dew23] [Sow20]

2.5.1 Straight Flanging

In the straight flanging method, the sheet is typically bent to usually 90 degrees along a flat die using a punch in a very simple way as shown in Figure 2.11 [Sow20].

In straight flanging process, the most common defect is springback, which occurs due to the elastic recovery of the sheet metal after the forming tool is removed. Figure 2.12 illustrates the springback effect [Liv01].

Figure 2.11 Straight flange [Sow20]

Figure 2.12 Springback effect [Liv01]

2.5.2 Stretch and Shrink Flanging

Stretch flanging is another type of flanging procedures where the product is flanged along a concave curvature, and the tensile forces act along the free edge of the flange [Dew23].

During the stretch flanging process, common defects such as cracking and fracturing of the sheet can occur. These defects occur due to excessive forming forces and high tensile stresses resulting from the change in radius. This is generally the most common type of failure in the stretch flanging process [Ans99].

In shrink flanging, the sheet is formed along a convex die to form the flange, and the major failure is considered to be wrinkling as the material accumulate at the edges due to the change in radius [Wan01]. Stretch and shrink flanges and wrinkling in shrink flanging are illustrated in Figure 2.13 [Vos13] [Liv04a] [Ste24a] [Ste22].

Figure 2.13 Stretch and shrink flanges (left) and wrinkling in shrink flanging (right) [Vos13] [Liv04a] [Ste24a] [Ste22]

In order to avoid wrinkling in shrink flanging, it is recommended to add a strategically placed material cut out in the blank before starting the shrink flanging process. This material cut out is usually called a flange relief, and it is very important to choose the suitable flange relief shape, size and location to achieve the best optimum design of the flange.

Although manufacturers generally have their own internal guidelines for selecting flange relief shapes, these practices are often considered proprietary and are not published in the scientific literature. Consequently, they are not fully accessible for systematic evaluation or standardization. Although flange reliefs are commonly used in practice, there has been no dedicated research investigating these relief shapes specifically for incremental sheet forming processes. Furthermore, most of the examples available in the literature are based on simple bending operations rather than more complex geometries and operations like those encoun-

tered in ISF. This highlights a notable gap that requires further study. Different flange relief designs are shown in Figure 2.14 [URLa] [Ste24b].

Figure 2.14 Some flange relief designs used in sheet metal forming operations [URLa] [Ste24b]

2.5.3 Hole Flanging

Flanging of a pre-cut hole in the sheet and forming from the inside toward the outside to create a flange around a hole is referred to as hole flanging process. In this process, the flange length increases and the diameter of the hole increases as well. Hole flanging is a conventional forming technique that creates a smooth cylindrical or conical hole flange. This process is carried on by punching a sheet blank with a concentric pre-cut hole while its outer edges maintained tightly by a blank holder [Dew23]. A schematic drawing for hole flange is shown in Figure 2.15 [Sow20].

Figure 2.15 Hole flange [Sow20]

In the hole flanging process, the blank deforms around the hole due to a combination of bending and stretching. Failure occurs due to necking or tearing at the edge of the flanges, which is caused by high circumferential strain values [Sil13].

2.6 Hemming Process

In the hemming process, sheet metals are joined together by bending them or folding them along their outer edges. The shape of the hem can vary depending on the desired product or the manufacturing requirements. Hemming may be carried out using either simple bending techniques or more complicated methods depending on the application and the final product requirements.

Hemming is a common manufacturing technique to connect metal sheets mechanically in order to build structural assemblies, and it is widely used in the automotive and aerospace sectors [Gür22]. In hemming, the sheet components are usually bent to 180 degree angle with the assistance of an inner sheet, producing a variety of parts that can be used in the automotive industry such as body panels, doors, hoods, tailgates and wheel arches [Dew20]. Figure 2.16 illustrates the main application areas of the hemming process in the automotive industry [Aut19].

Figure 2.16 Main application areas of hemming process in automotive industry [Aut19].

The process of hemming involves folding the edges of the outer sheet metal onto the inner sheet metal to create a permanent joint between the components [Gür22]. The sheet is bent to an angle of approximately 90 degrees in a process known as flanging, which have been discussed in section 2.5. After flanging, the sheet is bent to approximately 135 degrees in a process known as pre-hemming. And finally, the sheet is bent to approximately 180 degrees to create the final hem [Dew20]. Figure 2.17 illustrates the process of flanging, pre-hemming and hemming [Mao09] [Lie16].

Considering hemming as a mechanical joining technique that provides a durable connection between components, and because of the many benefits this process can provide. It is widely used in the automotive and aerospace sectors as previously mentioned. The advantages of this process include the ability to join different metallic or non-metallic materials. It is also possible to join sheets of different thicknesses using hemming. The most important ad-

vantage is avoiding thermal effects such as embrittlement or heat related distortion during the forming process. [Gür22]

Figure 2.17 Flanging, pre-hemming and hemming process [Mao09] [Lie16]

In order to create high quality hems, it is important to consider the materials ability to be hemmed due to the significant deformation that occurs during the flanging and hemming processes. Therefore, highly formable sheet metals are preferred for hemming operations.

The selection of the material for the sheet that is intended to be hemmed can be affected by many variables, including the materials own properties, such as precipitates at grain boundaries, component particles, surface roughening and bendability. The ability of the material to be hemmed and bent is enhanced by higher hardening values, precipitate-free grain boundaries, homogeneity in the component particles, and reduced surface roughness [Dao01]. Therefore, the most common materials used in hemming are steel and aluminium alloys due to their suitable material properties [Gür22]. The most frequently examined materials include aluminium alloys, such as AA1050, AA6111, AA6016, AA6061, and AA6022, which are known for their good formability and lightweight properties. Additionally, different steel grades like BH220, high strength steel, ultrahigh strength steel, and AISI 1070 steel have also been explored [Gür22].

Regardless of the material selected, the quality of the manufactured hems could be improved by applying sealant and adhesive materials to the joints. Sealant is typically applied to the closed edges of hemmed joints to protect them. The sealant acts as an anticorrosive agent by preventing moisture and other contaminants from entering the joint [Jia19] [Jia22].

Adhesives can be used on the surfaces where inner and outer panels overlap in order to provide more strength and stiffness to the joint as well as increasing the corrosion resistance of the sheet panels. Also adding adhesives to the joints is very important to reduce the vibrations of the sheet panels when subjected to external forces like wind or road vibrations. Therefore, increasing quality of the hemmed product especially in automotive applications where these vibrations can be noticeable. Adhesive materials are usually selected from epoxy-based materials, polyvinyl chloride, or even rubber materials [Mor04] [Gür22]. Figure 2.18 shows a hem with sealant and adhesive applied to it [Eur15].

Figure 2.18 Hem with sealant and adhesive [Eur15]

2.6.1 Hemming Process Classifications

In general, there are two main types of sheet metal hemming processes, the classical conventional method, and the roller method [Dew20]. In the classical conventional hemming process, a conventional punch such as a die is used to bend the sheet and it is divided into two categories, die hemming and table top hemming. The conventional hemming method typically consists of three steps: two pre-hemming stages and one final hemming stage [Mao10]. The conventional hemming process is illustrated in Figure 2.19 [URLb].

Figure 2.19 Conventional (table top) hemming process [URLb]

In the roller hemming process, a roller is used to bend the sheet metal in order to form the hems. Unlike conventional hemming, industrial robots enable roller hemming to benefit from a flexible manufacturing system. And over the past 20 years, roller hemming systems have replaced traditional hemming methods due to the significant benefits of flexible manufacturing systems [Gür22]. Figure 2.20 shows the hemming process using rollers [Hön14].

Figure 2.20 Roller hemming process [Hön14]

Using rollers instead of conventional hemming techniques also decreases the amount of surface defects and damage occurring to the hemmed part due to the flexibility and the reduced plastic strain value compared to conventional hemming, especially in the shrink flanged parts. Roller hemming is an incremental forming process, which explains the better formability observed in the parts produced by this technique. Figure 2.21 shows the difference in the bending zones of hems created by conventional hemming and roller hemming [Mao10].

Figure 2.21 Difference in bending zones of hems; (a) conventional hemming of convex edge and convex surface, (b) roller hemming of convex edge and convex surface, (c) conventional hemming of straight edge and convex surface, (d) roller hemming of straight edge and convex surface [Mao10]

2.6.2 Hem Types Variations

Once the hemming process is complete, including flanging, pre-hemming and final hemming to produce the hem joint, the resulting hem can be used in practical applications. To meet the

diverse requirements of these applications, hems of various types and shapes are formed using different tools and process conditions. [Gür22]

The most frequently used hem types are flat hems and rope hems. To achieve the desired product outcome, it is crucial to select the suitable hem type. The modified flat hem is essentially a variant of the flat hem and features a sharper hemming line and a smaller visible bending radius. This creates the illusion of a very narrow gap between adjacent car body panels. This makes it particularly suitable for applications requiring precise visual alignment [Bir13] [Gür22].

Rope hems, also known as droplet shaped hems, are typically used when the materials ductility is insufficient for forming flat hems. Additionally, rope hems are beneficial in enhancing pedestrian safety in the event of an accident [Bir13] [Gür22].

Flat hems, rope hems and their modified shapes are shown in Figure 2.22 [Gür22] [Zha00].

Figure 2.22 Some variations of hemming types [Gür22] [Zha00].

The hemming final shapes could also be customized depending on the final products requirements. And there are many applications for hemming such as barrels, tube ends and containers. Figure 2.23 illustrates various hem designs for final products purposes [Gür22] [Böl09].

Beyond hemming applications in complex designs and industrial processes. Hemming also finds its way into numerous everyday products, serving both functional and aesthetic purposes. Examples include the pull tabs on beverage cans, and the edges of clothes irons. Figure 2.24 illustrates some examples of these everyday products that incorporate hemming.

Figure 2.23 Various hem designs; (a) stand up hem, (b) lying hem, (c) stand up double hem, (d) lying double hem, (e) inside hem, (f) outside hem, (g) single bottom hem, (h) double bottom hem, (i) trapezium hem, and (j) taper hem [Böl09] [Gür22].

Figure 2.24 Clothes iron (left) and beverage can pull tab (right)

2.6.3 Hemming Geometries and Defects

Sheet geometries are usually categorized based on their surface shape and their edge shape. The sheet product geometry is very crucial to product quality and precision, and numerous common defects are directly correlated to the surface and edge shapes [Gür22]. Figure 2.25 illustrates the sheet panels geometries according to surface and edge shapes [Liv04b].

Figure 2.25 Sheet panels geometries according to surface and edge shapes [Liv04b]

The many variations in panel geometry will lead to manufacturing defects occurrence, and the likelihood of these defects occurring will increase as the panel geometry becomes more complicated. For example, a straight edge/flat surface geometry will have fewer defects than other geometries.

Some of these defects are roll-in and roll-out. They appear after the hemming operation as the edge of the folded panel could shift inward or outward. This causes a displacement from the original structure. When the displacement is inward, it is referred to as roll-in, and when the displacement is outward, it is referred to as roll-out [Gür22]. The roll-in and roll-out defects are important to consider in manufacturing design due to their direct effect on the panels final shape. This is due to their effect on the gap produced between the sheet panel and the inner sheet after the hemming process. Roll-in defects are more likely to arise on convex surface components, while the roll-out defects occur more in concave surface components. [Zha00] [Gür19a]

Other common defects like warp and recoil can occur during the forming process of hemming [Dew20]. Warp is known to be the collapsing of the outside surface in the hemming area. While recoil is the swelling of the outer panel. Recoil and warp formations in the outer sheet panels are caused by misalignment in components fixing [Gür19b]. Figure 2.26 shows the common hems defects [Liv04a].

Figure 2.26 The common hems defects [Liv04a]

2.6.4 Corner Hemming and Flange Relief (Cut-outs)

Parts with simple geometries containing straight edges and straight surfaces are generally easier to handle in hemming. While other complicated geometries like convex or concave surfaces might cause defects like material wrinkling and cracking [Vos13] [Ste24a]. Most of the industrial products are made up of sharp or curved geometries like the car doors or hoods. Therefore, the hemming research on complex geometries has become more common in order to address the practical manufacturing problems [Gür22]. Figure 2.27 illustrates the complex geometries in a car door [Liv04b] [Liv00].

Figure 2.27 Car door geometries [Liv04b] [Liv00]

Corner parts of car doors, sunroofs, hoods, and tailgates are frequently characterized by convex or sharp edge regions. Extra attention must be taken to prevent wrinkles from forming on these areas. And considering the fact that the flange height is the primary source of wrinkling formations, the flange height is generally decreased at corner zones [Sun12]. This

reduction in the flange length at the corner is called flange relief. Figure 2.28 shows the implementation of flange reliefs in hemming process [Gür22] [Sun12] [Ste24a].

The critical parameters in corner hemming are the corner radius and the flange length. In a study conducted by Sun et al, it was shown that increasing the corner radius helps to achieve a longer flange length, and decreasing the corner radius requires a shorter flange length to avoid wrinkling [Sun12] [VDI 3001].

Figure 2.28 Flange reliefs in hemming applications [Gür22] [Sun12] [Ste24a]

3 Motivation and Objective

In recent years, the automotive and aerospace industries have placed increasing emphasis on lightweight design to improve energy efficiency and reduce resource consumption. The adoption of multi material solutions including high strength steels, aluminium alloys, and composite materials has become increasingly widespread to meet these demands. However, as material combinations become more complex, conventional joining technologies such as welding are reaching their technical and economic limitations.

One of the primary challenges arises from complex geometries that involve sharp radii and corners. These features often lead to forming issues such as wrinkling, cracking, and dimensional inaccuracies. As a result, there is a growing demand for flexible joining techniques that can handle such complex geometries.

Incremental sheet forming presents a promising solution to address these challenges due to its high flexibility, cost effectiveness for small batch production, and ability to follow software-controlled toolpaths. Its localized forming nature allows for the gradual shaping of complex geometries without requiring dedicated dies for each component variation. While ISF has been widely studied for conventional forming tasks, its application to joining operations (specifically corner hemming) remains unexplored. This creates a significant research gap that necessitates a systematic investigation.

The objective of this study is to investigate the feasibility of corner hemming using ISF, and to develop an integrated process strategy covering the stages of flanging, pre-hemming, and final hemming. The study aims to analyse the influence of various factors such as flange relief designs, material removal surface areas, pre-hemming strategies, toolpath strategies, and flange length variations.

In alignment with these objectives, the following research questions are addressed:

- To what extent can joining connections on complex geometries, such as corners, be realized using incremental sheet forming?
- How do variations in flange relief designs, material removal area values, pre-hemming strategies, toolpath strategies, and flange lengths influence the corner hemming process and final part quality?
- What are the process limitations and optimal parameter configurations for achieving high quality corner hemming using incremental sheet forming?

Ultimately, this study contributes to expanding the process understanding and optimization strategies for corner hemming using ISF, thereby extending its potential application in future industrial manufacturing processes.

4 Experimental Procedures

The experimental methods and procedures used in the research are presented in this chapter. First, the chapter begins by describing the sheet metal material used in the experiments and the material used for the die. Afterwards, a summary of the machine used, the measurement systems and the forming tools applied in this research. Subsequently, the setup configuration, the methodology and the strategies of the experimental trials are introduced. Finally, the parameter variations and the strategies used to evaluate the samples feasibility are discussed.

4.1 Materials

4.1.1 DC04 Deep Drawing Steel

The material utilized for the experiments is DC04 cold-rolled deep drawing steel with a thickness of 1.0 mm, DC04 is well recognized for its material characteristics related to formability, ductility and deep drawing capabilities, making it a popular choice in industries such as automotive manufacturing for body panels, aerospace applications and other structural components. DC04 provides a reasonable balance between strength and plastic deformation, which makes it suitable for incremental sheet forming processes.

DC04 is an unalloyed steel, which makes it cost-effective and a reliable material solution for forming applications. On the other hand, DC04 does not have good corrosion resistance characteristics like stainless steel for example. In addition, DC04 is only suitable for applications that requires moderate mechanical loads. Additional surface treatments such as galvanizing or coatings are generally applied to enhance its corrosion resistance properties.

Table 1 shows the chemical composition and some of the mechanical properties for DC04 [DIN07].

In order to minimize the friction between the forming tool and the DC04 sheet metal during forming, a lubricant specifically developed for sheet metal forming operations and deep drawing operations was used. The lubricant was supplied by Zeller+Gmeinl.

Table 1: Chemical composition and mechanical properties of DC04 steel [DIN07]

DC04 Cold Rolled Steel			
$R_{p0.2}$ in MPa	R_m in MPa	ρ in g/cm ³	E in MPa
140-210	270-350	7.85	210000
C in %	Mn in %	P in %	S in %
0.08	0.40	0.03	0.03

$R_{p0.2}$: Yield strength at 0.2% offset; R_m : Maximum tensile stress; ρ : Density; E: Young's modulus; MPa: Mega Pascal; C: Carbon content; Mn: Manganese content; P: Phosphorus content; S: Sulfur content

4.1.2 Die Material (SikaBlock® M940)

SikaBlock® M940 polyurethane from Sika Deutschland GmbH was selected to manufacture the die used in the experiments. This material was a suitable choice due to its machinability and mechanical strength. Additionally, it offers a smooth and dense surface, which allows maintaining consistent contact during the forming process.

SikaBlock® M940 is typically used for casting molds and tooling in sheet metal applications, which makes it ideal for the kind of forming trials conducted in this research. The key mechanical properties of this material are summarized in Table 2 [Sik13].

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the die material (SikaBlock® M940) [Sik13]

SikaBlock® M940				
Shore hardness	Flexural strength in MPa	Compressive strength in MPa	ρ in g/cm ³	E in MPa
D 80	100	88	1.2	2500

4.2 Forming Machines, Measuring Systems and Tools

4.2.1 CNC Forming Machine – Amino DLNC-RB

All of the forming experiments conducted in this research were carried out by using a CNC controlled forming machine of the type AMINO DLNC-RB, developed by Amino Corporation. This machine is specifically designed for incremental sheet forming applications and operates by interpreting 3D toolpaths, which are generated from CAD models. It features a multi axis system in which the worktable moves along the X and Y axes, while the forming tool performs vertical motion along the Z direction. The worktable can also be synchronised with the tool, which is especially useful for dies with complex geometries.

The machine is equipped with a FANUC control system and offers precise control over the tool motion. It also can reach a forming speed of up to 30 m/min in the X and Y directions, and 10 m/min along the Z direction. The machine's maximum force is 0.5 kN in both X and Y, and up to 1.5 kN in Z, which is more than sufficient for shaping 1 mm thick DC04 steel sheets.

Figure 4.1 illustrates a photo of the machine, and Table 3 lists its important technical details [URLc].

Figure 4.1 CNC forming machine form Amino Corporation (left); worktable with tool during sheet forming (right) [URLc]

Table 3: Important technical details of Amino Corporation CNC forming machine [URLc]

Amino DLNC-RB	
Maximum forming speed	30 m/min in X and Y directions; 10 m/min in Z direction
Maximum machine forces	0.5 kN in X and Y directions; 1.5 kN in Z direction
Worktable space	500 x 500 x 250 mm ³ (L x W x H)

4.2.2 3D Optical Measurements – HandySCAN 700

In order to analyse the formed samples after the experiments, HandySCAN 700 from Creaform for 3D optical scanning was used. The HandySCAN 700 operates using a dual camera system along with a laser line projection to capture the geometrical details of the samples. This portable hand-held scanner captures the surface geometry of the formed parts with high precision, allowing generation of a full 3D mesh which can be directly compared to the original CAD models or other samples [Ker18].

The goal of using this measurements system was to assess the shape accuracy, detect deviations, and measure the samples structural features like flange lengths. Figure 4.2 shows the HandySCAN 700 device, while Table 4 lists the key functional specifications [Ker18].

Table 4: Key functional specifications of Creafom HandySCAN 700 [Ker18]

HandySCAN 700			
Scan method	Scan speed [pts/s] (points per second)	Range [m]	Accuracy [mm]
Stereo photogrammetry	480000	0.3–4.0	0.02+0.06/m

Figure 4.2 HandySCAN 700 device (left); a sample and its corresponding scan mesh (right)

4.2.3 GOM Inspect

In order to analyse the accuracy of the formed parts, GOM Inspect 2018 was used for all post-processing evaluations. This software helped in comparing the scanned 3D models of the samples with the original CAD data as well as comparing different samples with each other by highlighting dimensional differences. GOM Inspect was mainly used to inspect features like lengths, radii, and overall geometry. The software also allows the possibility of generating cross sections and reference points for more detailed evaluations.

4.2.4 Forming Tools

In this study, three different forming tools were used, each chosen for their suitability for different stages of the incremental sheet forming process. The 20 mm diameter spherical tool was used mainly for all flanging and final hemming processes, the 20 mm tool provides a good balance between good formability and moderated distribution of stress concentration. The 10 mm tools consisting of one regular 10 mm diameter ISF tool and another customized 10 mm diameter tool with a 2 mm tip radius were both used for pre-hemming operations, they were used to bend the flanges to approximately 90 degrees. The smaller tool size offered better engagement with the short flange lengths. In comparison, the 20 mm tool was not suitable for pre-hemming operations due its large geometry as the flanges tended to slip

underneath the tool, and it was impossible to reach the desired flange angle using 20 mm tool. This will be discussed more in details in the following chapters.

Figure 4.3 shows the three types of tools used in the experiments.

Figure 4.3 ISF tools used in the experiments

4.3 Experimental Setup

4.3.1 Die Structure, Fixation Method, Zero Clamp and Die Adapter Plates

The die used in this research was designed to accommodate four different corner radii within one die. The same sheet was formed over four different radii under identical process conditions. The die features radii of 5 mm, 10 mm, 15 mm, and 20 mm located on each corner.

The overall die dimensions were 100 mm length and 100 mm width including 90 mm straight part and 5 mm bending radius on each side, and the total height of the die is 90 mm. The following Figure 4.4 describes the die geometries in details.

Figure 4.4 Die geometries

To secure the sheet metal during the forming, a simple but stable fixation system was employed. The setup included two 8 mm diameter pins positioned on the sides of the die. Along with a central M8 screw fitted with a small ring, the small ring provided additional surface contact improving overall stability. In addition to the small ring, the inner sheet was fixed as well. Proper fixation is critical in incremental sheet forming to prevent the sheet from moving during tool movement, especially when forming near edges or corners. Figure 4.5 illustrates the fixation method.

Figure 4.5 Fixation method

In order to mount the forming die securely on the Amino machine, the zero clamp plate was installed on the machine's worktable. This clamping system is pneumatically activated and ensures highly stable and level surface, which is essential for the stability of the system. However, as the main forming die was not compatible with the zero clamp plate, a custom die adapter was designed and used as an intermediate connection between the main forming die and the zero clamp plate. Figure 4.6 shows the zero clamp plate and the die adapter.

Figure 4.6 Zero clamp plate and die adapter

4.3.2 Sheet Metal Samples Design

In this research, several sheet metal samples were designed to investigate the geometrical influences on convex flanging and hemming operations through the incremental sheet forming technique. The samples differed in overall length (desired flange length) as well as in the shape of the flange reliefs. These design modifications were implemented to investigate how factors such as flange length, flange relief geometry and the value of removed material surface area (cut-out surface area) affect the dimensional accuracy and the occurrence of defects like cracking or wrinkling. An overview of the flange relief sample designs is provided in Figure 4.7, all the designing parameters will be explained in the following sections.

Figure 4.7 Flange relief sample designs

The experiments were conducted over four different experimental series. Each series focused on a specific set of variables, which allowed evaluating different parameters in the process.

4.3.3 Experimental Series I (Feasibility of Flange Relief Designs)

In the first experimental series, the focus was on evaluating the influence of difference flange relief shapes at the corners. The sheet sample had dimensions of 117.708 mm in length and width. This value was based on a theoretical approach of 90 mm straight section and 7.854 mm on each side to cover the die curvature as well as 6 mm as a desired flange length as shown in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8 Sample length in experimental series I

Four distinct flange relief shapes were designed for the experimental series I; square, quarter circle, linear 45° and the smooth transition. The flange reliefs were adjusted to accommodate the die corner radii (5 mm, 10 mm, 15 mm, and 20 mm) and most importantly, the distance between the die corner tip and the start of the flange remained constant. This means that each corner radius resulted in a different amount of material removal (cut-out surface area), and the 20 mm radius corner resulted in the greatest material removal value.

4.3.3.1 Square Flange Relief

For the square flange relief, the overall dimensions were 117.708 mm as discussed before. The main reference corner radius used was the 5 mm corner radius as it is the smallest corner radius value. To create the flange relief, 6 mm * 6 mm square cut was removed from the 5 mm corner as shown in Figure 4.9. Then the distance between the 5 mm corner radius and the start of the flange relief was measured and implemented in all the other corners as shown in Figure 4.9 . This constant distance was approximately 6 mm for all cases in experimental series I except for the quarter circle flange relief as it was approximately 8.5 mm.

Figure 4.9 Square flange relief

4.3.3.2 Quarter Circle Flange Relief

Similar concept as the previous square flange relief in terms of using the 5 mm corner radius as base reference and fixing the distance between the corner tip and the start of the flange. The only difference is in the actual flange relief geometry as its circular shaped. Figure 4.10 illustrates the quarter circle flange relief.

Figure 4.10 Quarter circle flange relief

4.3.3.3 Linear 45° Flange Relief

In this variation, the concept remains similar. The same sheet dimensions and fixing the 5 mm corner radius as a base reference point was applied. The flange relief formed a chamfer shape as shown in Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.11 Linear 45° flange relief

4.3.3.4 Smooth Transition Flange Relief

This flange relief shape was designed using a series of blended curves, the 5 mm corner radius served as the reference point for the distance similar to the previous three types. The side length of the flange relief was chosen to be 18.5 mm. The 18.5 mm consists of the 6 mm desired flange length and another 11.5 mm in order to ensure a smooth transition and to provide sufficient amount of material removal. All the curves within the corner range have a radius of 6 mm in order to match with the theoretical flange length. Figure 4.12 shows the smooth transition flange relief.

Figure 4.12 Smooth transition flange relief

4.3.3.5 Comparison Between Flange Reliefs Shapes

A comparison of the four flange relief shapes revealed clear differences in the amount of material removed surface area. These differences depend on the corner radius and the flange relief shape. For the corner radius, it was clear that increasing corner radius will lead

to more material removal in order to comply with the fixed distance between the die corner tip and the start of the flange. As for the flange relief shape, the smooth transition flange relief resulted in the largest material removal, followed by the linear 45°, and both square and quarter circle flange reliefs had lower values of material removal. The following Table 5 shows the amount of material removal for the samples in experimental series I.

Table 5: Amount of material removal for the samples (experimental series I)

Corner radius (mm)	Removed material surface area (mm ²)			
	Square	Quarter circle	Linear 45°	Smooth transition
5	36	28.27	72	79.07
10	56	48	112	140.9
15	78.56	72.17	160.13	215.6
20	108.02	100.69	216.04	310.34

4.3.4 Experimental Series II (Evaluation of Pre-Hemming and Hemming Tool-path Strategies)

Experimental series II focused on analysing the effects of two distinct flange relief geometries: Linear 45° and smooth transition. The sheet metal samples used in this series had a total length of 107 mm, composed of a 90 mm straight section, two 2.5 mm extensions on each side to accommodate the die geometry, and 6 mm flange lengths at both ends. Importantly, all four corners of each sample featured identical flange relief shapes, ensuring that the material removal area remained constant across the entire specimen. Figure 4.13 shows the sample dimensions.

Figure 4.13 Sample dimensions in experimental series II

4.3.4.1 Linear 45° Flange Relief

The design approach was fundamentally similar to that used in experimental series I. However, a notable change was made to the overall sample length, which was adjusted to 107 mm. In experimental series II, the linear 45° flange relief was applied across all four corners of the sample and the material removal area of 72 mm² was the same at all corners. Figure 4.14 illustrates the linear 45° flange relief in experimental series II.

Figure 4.14 Linear 45° flange relief

4.3.4.2 Smooth Transition Flange Relief

In experimental series II, the smooth transition flange relief was implemented with a continuous curvature at all four corners, replacing the multi curve approach used in experimental series I. Although the flange relief shape was modified, the design principles remained con-

sistent with 18.5 mm allocated from each corner to maintain a gradual smooth material flow. Additionally, the sample length was adjusted to 107 mm, differentiating this series from the previous one. The following Figure 4.15 shows the smooth transition sample used in experimental series II.

Figure 4.15 Smooth transition flange relief

Amount of material removal in experimental series II

The comparison between linear 45° and the smooth transition flange reliefs reveals a clear difference in the amount of the material removed from the corners. The following Table 6 shows the amount of material removal surface area for the samples in experimental series II.

Table 6: Amount of material removal for the samples (experimental series II)

Corner radius (mm)	Removed material surface area (mm ²)	
	Linear 45°	Smooth transition
5, 10, 15, 20	72	89

4.3.5 Experimental Series III (Impact of Flange Length Reduction on Hemming)

Experimental series III focused on evaluating the performance of linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief geometries under modified flange dimensions. The total sample length was reduced to 103 mm, comprising a 90 mm straight section, 2.5 mm on both sides to accommodate the die geometry, and 4 mm flange lengths on each side. As in the previous series, the same flange relief design was applied at all four corners, ensuring that the material removal area was similar for all corners. Figure 4.16 illustrates the samples dimensions and geometries.

Figure 4.16 Sample dimensions in experimental series III

Design Parameters and amount of material removal in experimental series III

The design parameters for both samples in experimental series III were similar with those used in series II, with the exception of the smooth transition sample. In this case, the flange relief side length was reduced from 18.5 mm to 13.5 mm to match the shorter flange length. This revised length includes 4 mm for the desired flange length and an additional 9.5 mm to ensure a smooth material flow within the flange relief geometry as shown in Figure 4.16.

As for the amount of the material removed from the corners. The following Table 7 shows the amount of material removal from the samples in experimental series III.

Table 7: Amount of material removal for the samples (experimental series III)

Corner radius (mm)	Removed material surface area (mm ²)	
	Linear 45°	Smooth transition
5, 10, 15, 20	32	39

4.3.6 Experimental Series IV (Effect of Equal Material Removal Value on Different Flange Relief Designs)

In experimental series IV, the testing focused exclusively on the linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief geometries, using a sample length of 107 mm, similar to experimental series II. In this series, the flange relief geometry was applied to all four corners of each sample with almost identical material removal value across the corners. A key modification in this series was the adaptation of the linear 45° flange relief to closely match the material removal value of the smooth transition flange relief, resulting in a comparable removed area of approximately 88 mm² for the linear 45° flange relief and 89 mm² for the smooth transition flange relief. To distinguish between the original linear 45° design and the adjusted version, the adjusted linear 45° flange relief will be referred to as linear 45° B in the following sections. Figure 4.17 shows the samples used in experimental series IV, while table 8 shows the amount of material removal for each flange relief design.

This variation aims to isolate and identify the impact of different flange relief shapes under almost identical material removal values.

Figure 4.17 Samples used in experimental series IV

Table 8: Amount of material removal for the samples (experimental series IV)

Corner radius (mm)	Removed material surface area (mm ²)	
	Linear 45° B	Smooth transition
5, 10, 15, 20	88	89

4.3.7 Inner Sheet Design

Hemming is a mechanical joining technique where two sheets are joined together along their outer edges through controlled bending and folding operations. While the outer sheet design, including the flange relief characteristics, plays a critical role in the forming process. It is

important to properly design the inner sheets to ensure they can be securely inserted into the hemming setup.

For all experiments in this study, the inner sheet thickness was 1 mm. The overall dimensions of the inner sheet were set to 93 mm, providing a 1.5 mm overlap on each side with respect to the inner die contour dimension of 90 mm.

The design of the inner sheet corners was directly derived from the interior contour of the forming die, with adjustments made to avoid excessive sharpness at smaller radii. Specifically, a 15 mm inner die corner radius corresponded to a 16.5 mm inner sheet corner radius, a 10 mm inner die corner to a 11.5 mm inner sheet corner, a 5 mm inner die corner to a 6.5 mm inner sheet corner, and finally, the sharp inner die corner was adjusted to a 1.5 mm inner sheet corner radius to prevent sharp edges. Figure 4.18 shows the inner sheet design concept.

Figure 4.18 Inner sheet design concept

4.4 Flanging

Although a detailed investigation of the flanging process falls outside the core scope of this research, flanging serves as a critical preparatory step for conducting the hemming experiments. Therefore, proper flange formation is essential to create good quality hemming experiments.

All sheet metal samples were mounted onto the forming die as previously described in section 4.3.1. For the flanging operations, a 20 mm diameter forming tool was utilized, and a vertical step size of 1 mm was applied. To minimize the possibility of collisions between the tool and the die, a safety distance of 0.1 mm was included in the setup, so that the distance

between the tool tip and the die is 1.1 mm consisting of 1 mm sheet thickness and the safety distance. The feed rate value was 2000 mm/min.

The toolpath employed was circular and reversible, in a way that at each vertical step, the direction of the tool movement was reversed. This means that if one pass was formed in a clockwise direction, the next would proceed in a counter clockwise direction, and so on. Figure 4.19 shows the toolpath used in creating the flanges.

Figure 4.19 Flanging toolpath

These parameters were selected in alignment with the experimental parameters defined by Voswinckel et al. [Vos13] in their research about flanging by means of incremental sheet forming.

The following Figure 4.20 illustrates a selection of samples produced during the flanging stage of experimental series I, highlighting the different flange relief geometries.

Figure 4.20 Samples produced during the flanging stage of experimental series I

4.4.1 Preliminary Findings of Flanging in Experimental Series I

In experimental series I, the flanges produced from the various flange relief designs were analysed to assess their dimensional characteristics. This evaluation was aiming to identify the most promising flanges and flange relief shapes in terms of geometric accuracy and surface defects. Based on these findings, the samples which exhibited favourable flanging characteristics were selected to proceed further into the hemming experiments.

The analysis of the flanges was based on flange height measurements using GOM Inspect software. By measuring the distance from the base sheet line to the outer edge of the flange as shown in Figure 4.21.

Figure 4.21 Flange height measurements

The following preliminary findings summarize the observed behaviours for each flange relief shape. While Figure 4.22 illustrates the flange height measurements for each sample in experimental series I.

Figure 4.22 Samples flange height measurements in experimental series I

Square flange relief

This flange relief shape showed a greater tendency to crack initiation, especially at sharp corners. Flange length increased at the corners, and larger corner radii resulted in longer flange lengths, whereas smaller radii increased the risk of wrinkling. The straight flange regions exhibited only partial homogeneity. Additionally, the sharp edges of the flange relief design caused damage to the die surface. Overall, this flange relief design failed during the hemming process.

Quarter circle flange relief

Similar to the square flange relief, this geometry was susceptible to crack initiation. The flange length increased at the corners, and larger corner radii resulted in longer lengths, while smaller radii were associated with a greater risk of wrinkling. The straight flange sections were less homogeneous than the square flange relief. Die damage was also observed due to the sharp corners in the flange design. This flange relief configuration was unsuccessful in the hemming operation.

Linear 45° flange relief

The linear 45° flange relief design was less susceptible to crack initiation. Unlike previous designs, the flange length remained consistent and did not increase at the corners. Although there was still a risk of wrinkling at smaller corner radii, it was significantly less severe. The straight flange areas exhibited improved homogeneity. Minor die damage was observed due to sharp edges in the flange relief, but the sample successfully passed the hemming process.

Smooth transition flange relief

This flange relief configuration was also less susceptible to crack initiation. While smaller corner radii still posed a risk of wrinkling, the issue was less prominent, and the flange length remained stable across the corners. The straight flanges exhibited a high level of homogeneity. This flange relief design successfully completed the hemming process.

In summary, while sharp-edged designs (square and quarter circle) induced multiple failure modes like wrinkling, and less homogeneity in straight flanges areas accompanied with die wear. The linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs demonstrated better performance in terms of homogeneity in straight flanges areas with no flange length increasing at the corners, and importantly the capability to be hemmed. As a result, the linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs were selected to proceed for the subsequent hemming experiments.

4.4.2 Flanging of Experimental Series II, III and IV

The flanging results in experimental series II, III, and IV showed noticeable better results compared to experimental series I. One of the contributing factors to this was the reduction of the total sample length to 107 mm in series II and IV, and further down to 103 mm in series III. Another contributing factor was limiting the investigations to only the linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs due to their improved geometric characteristics compared to the other flange relief shapes in experimental series I.

The following Figure 4.23 present a selection of flanged samples produced in experimental series II.

Figure 4.23 Flanges produced in experimental series II

4.5 Pre-Hemming

In preparation for the hemming process, it was necessary to first perform a pre-hemming operation. This step involved flipping the formed flange upside down to enable the insertion of the inner sheet and creating the final hem. The process stages before hemming are shown in Figure 4.24.

Figure 4.24 Process stages before hemming

However, after the flanging stage, the resulting flange angle was insufficient for direct hemming. This limitation posed a significant issue, as the sheet tended to slip underneath the 20 mm diameter hemming tool during forming, preventing proper contact between the forming tool and the sheet. The primary reason for this inadequate flange angle was attributed to the 5 mm bending radius incorporated into the forming die as shown previously in Figure 4.4.

To overcome this issue, a pre-hemming operation was introduced to partially bend the flange, thereby correcting its angle and minimizing the risk of slipping during the subsequent hemming stage. Initially, a hemispherical incremental forming tool with a 10 mm diameter was employed for this purpose. However, in order to achieve a greater vertical movement of the tool without interference with the die surface, the tool was later replaced by a customized 10 mm diameter tool featuring a modified tip geometry as shown previously in Figure 4.3.

The customized tool achieved better contact point with the sheet which helped achieving better pre-hemming angle. Figure 4.25 illustrates the concept of the customized tool.

Figure 4.25 Concept of the customized tool

4.5.1 Pre-Hemming Strategies

For the pre-hemming operations, two different toolpath strategies were implemented. In strategy 1 (pre-hemming with corner forming), the toolpath was programmed to follow the entire flange contour, including the corner regions, allowing the corners to be formed simultaneously with the straight flange sections. In contrast, strategy 2 (pre-hemming without corner forming) was limited to the straight sections of the flange, excluding the corners from forming. For both strategies, the toolpath was circular and reversible similar to the flanging toolpath and a horizontal step size of 0.5 mm with 2000 mm/min feed rate value was applied. After the sample was flipped following the flanging operation, the corner radii of 20 mm and 10 mm switched positions. Figure 4.26 illustrates the toolpaths used in pre-hemming stage.

Figure 4.26 Pre-hemming toolpaths

The following Figure 4.27 shows the flanges produced after applying both pre-hemming toolpath strategies, and the difference in corners shape can be seen clearly.

Figure 4.27 Flanges produced after pre-hemming

4.5.2 Preliminary Findings of Pre-Hemming

The preliminary evaluation of the two pre-hemming strategies revealed that strategy 1 (pre-hemming with corner forming) demonstrated better performance in terms of the resultant hem geometry. As shown in the following Figure 4.28, it can be observed that when using strategy 1, the corners exhibit a more rounded shape. While, the corners produced with strategy 2 (pre-hemming without corner forming) appear to be partially folded, resulting in sharper edges.

Figure 4.28 Hems produced using pre-hemming strategy 1 and strategy 2

Based on the findings from the pre-hemming trials, it was decided that strategy 1 provided better corner geometry and overall hem quality. Therefore, all subsequent hemming experiments were conducted using the pre-hemming strategy 1 toolpath.

4.6 Hemming

The hemming process was performed to finalize the edge folding and produce the desired hem geometry. While each experimental series (I, II, III, and IV) exhibited unique outcomes and challenges during the entire process, which will be discussed in detail later in this chapter.

A unified set of process parameters was applied across all trials. A 20 mm diameter hemispherical forming tool was used throughout the hemming operations, and a horizontal step size of 0.5 mm was applied. Additionally, no intrusion depth was introduced during the hemming process and the feed rate value was 2000 mm/min.

To accurately follow the specific corner geometries of the samples, the hemming toolpath was programmed with a fixed contour radius that corresponded to the respective corner radius of each sample. For example, when hemming the corner with the 20 mm radius, the toolpath was generated using a 20 mm contour radius, and when hemming the corner with the 5 mm radius, the toolpath had a 5 mm contour radius. The toolpath was circular and reversible similar to the flanging and pre-hemming toolpaths. The following Figure 4.29 explains the toolpath design.

Figure 4.29 Hemming toolpath design

The tool tip height was designed to be 3 mm above the forming die, consisting of 1 mm for the lower part, 1 mm for the inner sheet, and 1 mm corresponding to the portion of the flange intended to be hemmed. Figure 4.30 shows the concept of the tool tip height.

Figure 4.30 Concept of the tool tip height

4.6.1 Hemming in Experimental Series I

The hemming operations in experimental series I primarily focused on evaluating the suitability of the different flange relief geometries for the hemming process. The samples used in this series were previously described in section 4.3.3. Since the flange lengths in this series were relatively long, no pre-hemming was required as the flange did not slip under the forming tool.

The hemming was performed using the general process parameters established earlier. A 20 mm diameter tool, 0.5 mm step size, and toolpaths adjusted to match the corner radii. No intrusion depth was applied during the process. And the feed rate value was 2000 mm/min.

The results revealed significant differences between the flange relief geometries. The square and quarter circle flange reliefs failed completely during the hemming process. In contrast, the linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs successfully completed the hemming operation, though the overall geometric quality of the hemmed parts was still not fully satisfactory. It is important to clarify that when the process is described as unsuccessful during the hemming operation, this indicates that the sample was severely damaged, making it impossible to form a functional hem.

These findings provided an initial indication of which relief designs were more suitable for further investigations in the following experimental series. Figure 4.31 shows the square flange relief sample which failed during hemming operation, and Figure 4.32 shows the linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief resultant hems.

Figure 4.31 Square flange relief sample (failed during hemming)

Linear 45° flange relief

Smooth transition flange relief

Figure 4.32 Linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief hems produced in experimental series I.

4.6.2 Hemming in Experimental Series II

The hemming operations in experimental series II were divided into two parts. The first part which was executed and explained in section 4.5.2, focused on identifying the most suitable pre-hemming strategy. While the second part was dedicated to evaluating different toolpath strategies on the resulting hemming geometry after applying the recommended pre-hemming approach.

As previously described in section 4.5.2, strategy 1 was identified as the more effective pre-hemming approach. Therefore, all hemming samples discussed in the following sections were processed using pre-hemming strategy 1 in combination with the customized 10 mm diameter tool described in section 4.5 and Figure 4.24.

In experimental series II, two different hemming toolpath strategies were implemented to investigate their influence on the forming results. The first strategy consisted of a single continuous stage, similar to the approach previously applied in experimental series I, where the entire flange contour was hemmed in one uninterrupted operation. The second strategy involved a two stage forming process: in the first stage, only the corners of the samples were hemmed, followed by a second stage where the remaining straight sections of the flange were continuously hemmed. Figure 4.33 illustrates the toolpath used in strategy 2. It can be noticed that after flipping the sample following the flanging process, the 20 mm and 10 mm corner radii exchanged positions.

Figure 4.33 Toolpath used in strategy 2

The samples used for this series were introduced in section 4.3.4, featuring both linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief geometries. The hemming was conducted using the same general parameters applied in the previous experiments (tool diameter, step size, intrusion depth and feed rate).

All samples successfully passed the hemming process. Figure 4.34 shows the linear 45° hems produced in experimental series II, and Figure 4.35 shows the smooth transition hems produced in experimental series II. However, it should be noted that the hems produced using the single stage forming strategy were considered as successful hems. While the hems

produced using the two stage forming strategy did not meet the required quality and were therefore not considered successful hems.

One continuous forming stage strategy

Two forming stages strategy

Figure 4.34 Linear 45° hems produced in experimental series II

One continuous forming stage strategy

Two forming stages strategy

Figure 4.35 Smooth transition hems produced in experimental series II

4.6.3 Hemming in Experimental Series III

The hemming operations in experimental series III focused on evaluating the process behaviour when reducing the flange length. This adjustment aimed to investigate how shorter flanges affect the quality of the hems produced.

Similar to the approach used in experimental series II, pre-hemming strategy 1 was applied in combination with the customized 10 mm diameter tool. The samples used in this series were previously introduced in section 4.3.5, featuring both linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief designs.

The hemming operations were carried out using the same general process parameters applied in the earlier series (tool diameter, step size, intrusion depth and feed rate). Two different toolpath strategies were applied in this series as well: a single stage continuous forming strategy, and a two stage forming strategy, where the corners were hemmed first, followed by continuous hemming of the straight flange sections.

All samples successfully passed the hemming process and similarly to experimental series II, the hems produced using the single stage forming strategy were considered to be successful hems. And the hems produced using the two stage forming strategy did not meet the required quality and were therefore not considered successful. Figure 4.36 and Figure 4.37 shows the hems produced in experimental series III for both linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs.

Figure 4.36 Linear 45° hems produced in experimental series III

Figure 4.37 Smooth transition hems produced in experimental series III

4.6.4 Hemming in Experimental Series IV

The hemming operations in experimental series IV focused on assessing the influence of the material removal value on the final hemming results. This variation aimed to investigate how different flange relief designs would behave under almost identical material removal values.

Similar to the previous series, pre-hemming strategy 1 was applied using the customized 10 mm diameter tool and the samples used in this series were previously described in section 4.3.6, and included both linear 45° B and smooth transition flange relief designs.

The hemming operations were carried out using the same general process parameters as in the earlier series (tool diameter, step size, intrusion depth and feed rate) and the same tool-path strategies (continuous single stage and two stages forming).

The hems produced using the single stage forming strategy were considered to be successful hems for both flange relief designs, consistent with the results obtained in the previous experimental series. However, it was observed that the linear 45° B flange relief sample, which had a material removal value of 88 mm², unexpectedly demonstrated a relatively good hemming result when using the two stage forming strategy, therefore, it was considered to be a successful hem. Figure 4.38 shows the hems produced in experimental series IV for linear 45° B, while the smooth transition flange relief was previously shown in Figure 4.35.

One continuous forming stage strategy

Two forming stages strategy

Figure 4.38 Linear 45° B hems produced in experimental series IV

5 Results and Discussion

This chapter is organised into five distinct sections to comprehensively evaluate the outcomes of the experiments. Each section focuses on a different aspect of the hemming results. The discussion begins with an overview of the experiments, presenting a comparative table to distinguish between successful and unsuccessful hemming processes and resulting hems. The second section provides detailed observations of wrinkling, highlighting the areas where it occurred and its correlation with the implemented toolpaths. The third section involves measuring the corner radii of the formed hems, offering insight into the geometric accuracy of the corners across different samples. The corner gap analysis then focuses on evaluating the extent of gaps in tight radius corners. Finally, the hem outer contour analysis compares the theoretical and achieved outer contour profiles, emphasising deviations in shape continuity and homogeneity.

5.1 Overview of the Experiments

This section provides an overview of the hemming results obtained from all experimental series. A summary table is included to indicate which samples failed during the hemming process and which successfully completed the operation. Among the samples that passed the hemming process, further distinction is made between those that resulted in successful hems, and those considered unsuccessful due to defects such as wrinkles, or significant deviations from the intended geometry.

The summary of the experiments is described in Table 9. A few key observations can be drawn from the table. In experimental series I (see section 4.6.1), flange relief geometry significantly influenced the outcome. The square and quarter circle designs failed entirely due to severe damage during the hemming operation. Although the linear 45° and smooth transition designs completed the hemming process, the final hems were unsuccessful due to defects like wrinkling at corners.

In experimental series II and III (see section 4.6.2 and 4.6.3), where the toolpath strategy was varied, a clear trend emerged. The single stage continuous forming strategy produced successful final hems for both linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs, whereas the two stage strategy resulted in unsuccessful hems despite passing the hemming operation. This suggests that a continuous forming approach offers greater control over the hemming process and reduces the likelihood of wrinkling occurring, and cuts down the overall process time.

In series IV (see section 4.6.4), successful hems were produced using both single stage and two stage toolpaths with the modified linear 45° B flange relief, showing that increasing the material removal value can overcome the limitations of the two stage toolpath strategy.

The table clearly shows the link between flange relief design and forming strategy on hem quality. Single stage forming was found to be more reliable, with flange relief designs featuring smooth transition or linear 45° offering better process results.

Table 9: Summary of experiments

Experimental series	Flange relief	Hemming process	Final hem	
			1-stage	2-stage
Experimental series I	Square	Failed	---	
	Quarter circle	Failed	---	
	Linear 45°	Passed	Unsuccessful	
	Smooth transition	Passed	Unsuccessful	
			Toolpath	
Experimental series II	Linear 45°	Passed	Successful	Unsuccessful
	Smooth transition	Passed	Successful	Unsuccessful
Experimental series III	Linear 45°	Passed	Successful	Unsuccessful
	Smooth transition	Passed	Successful	Unsuccessful
Experimental series IV	Linear 45° B	Passed	Successful	Successful

5.2 Wrinkling Observations

Wrinkling remains one of the most critical challenges in sheet metal hemming, particularly at corners due to the change in radii. In experimental series I, visible wrinkling was observed at the 5 mm and 10 mm corner radii, suggesting a correlation between longer flange lengths and increased susceptibility to wrinkling in tighter curves. Although both linear and smooth flange relief geometries were tested, the linear 45° flange relief exhibited relatively improved hemming results in terms of wrinkling at corners as shown in Figure 4.32. The following Figure 5.1 shows wrinkling in experimental series I.

Figure 5.1 Wrinkling in experimental series I

The experiments conducted in series II, III, and IV revealed that wrinkling was closely associated with the two stage forming strategy, regardless of the flange relief geometry employed. This highlights the better performance of the single stage continuous hemming toolpath. It can be noticed that wrinkles predominantly occur at corner regions, specifically at the edges corresponding to the beginning and ending points of the first toolpath stage (illustration of the toolpath is shown in Figure 4.33). Also, it can be seen that the linear 45° B used in experimental series IV demonstrated noticeable improvement in minimising wrinkling. Figure 5.2, Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4 illustrate the extent and location of the wrinkles observed across experimental series II, III and IV.

Figure 5.2 Wrinkling in experimental series II (two stage forming toolpath)

Figure 5.3 Wrinkling in experimental series III (two stage forming toolpath)

Figure 5.4 Wrinkling in experimental series IV (two stage forming toolpath)

5.3 Corner Radii Analysis

To evaluate the forming accuracy of the corner regions, this section compares the actual radii of the produced hems against the target values of 15 mm and 20 mm corner radii provided by the die geometry. The evaluation in this section was limited to the 15 mm and 20 mm corner radii, as the 5 mm and 10 mm corners were excluded due to the presence of wrinkling and non-uniform outer contours.

The outer contours of the resulting hems were captured using 3D scanning, and the radii were measured using GOM Inspect software. The following Figure 5.5 illustrates the testing methodology for the corner radii analysis.

Figure 5.5 Testing methodology for the corner radii analysis

A total of six samples were analysed, those samples represented all the successful hems as referred to in Table 9, the majority of which were manufactured using the one stage continuous forming strategy. The samples included variations in flange relief design and flange length: 6 mm smooth transition and 6 mm linear 45° (from experimental series II), 4 mm smooth transition and 4 mm linear 45° (from experimental series III), and the adjusted 6 mm linear 45° B (both single stage and two stage forming from experimental series IV).

Each sample corner geometry was measured using the 3D optical measurement (Handy-SCAN700) and GOM Inspect software described in sections 4.2.2 and 4.2.3, and the resulting corner radii were extracted and plotted. This comparison aims to assess how different flange relief geometries and flange lengths influence the resultant hem geometry and corner radii. Figure 5.6 shows the achieved corner radii for the samples.

Figure 5.6 Corner radii analysis

The analysis reveals a correlation between flange length and the resulting corner radii of the hemmed samples. Specifically, samples with greater flange length exhibited results that closely matched the 20 mm target radius. However, these same samples showed less accuracy in forming the 15 mm radius.

Conversely, samples with shorter flange length tended to produce corners that were closer to the 15 mm radius target, while showing greater deviation from the 20 mm radius. This suggests that shorter flange lengths are more suitable for tighter radii.

The samples with shorter flange length investigated previously were generally considered to be successful, as the wrinkles were not particularly severe. However, minor wrinkling at the edges of the 20 mm corners likely contributed to the larger radius value observed in those areas (see Figure 4.36 and Figure 4.37). This explains the overshooting value over the target 20 mm radius.

The comparison between the linear 45° B samples formed using the one stage and two stage forming strategies revealed similar results at the 20 mm corner radii. However, when evaluating the 15 mm corner radii, both samples performed unsatisfactorily, producing significantly sharper corners than intended.

5.4 Corner Gaps Analysis

This section presents an evaluation of the final resultant hems based on the measurement of corner gaps. The focus is specifically on the 5 mm and 10 mm corner radii, as the 15 mm and 20 mm corners were mostly fully closed in all cases and therefore did not present significant variation.

For the evaluation of the corner gaps in the produced hems, the measurement approach was applied using the overall 3D scans of the final formed hems, and GOM Inspect software was used to measure the gaps at the 5 mm and 10 mm corner radii. The measurement procedure involved identifying the central region of each corner gap and drawing a linear line across the opening to represent the gap width. Figure 5.7 shows the testing methodology for the corner gaps analysis.

Figure 5.7 Testing methodology for the corner gaps analysis

The samples included in this analysis were the same as the corner radii analysis in the previous section 5.3. The gap values at the corners were measured and compared to identify the influence of flange relief design and flange length on hemming tightness and closure. Figure 5.8 shows the values of the gaps observed in the samples.

Figure 5.8 Corner gaps analysis

The analysis of corner gaps revealed that the linear 45° flange relief consistently exhibited lower gap values compared to the smooth transition flange relief. This observation can be attributed to the lower material removal value in the linear 45° flange relief design compared to the smooth transition flange relief (see Table 5, Table 6, and Table 7), which helped in maintaining a tighter closure in the resultant hems. This trend is further supported when comparing the original linear 45° sample to the adjusted linear 45° B sample. While the original sample achieved nearly zero gap at the corners, the linear 45° B sample, which featured a higher material removal value, exhibited a gap of approximately 2 mm at both 5 mm and 10 mm corners during the single stage forming and approximately 4 mm for the two stage forming.

5.5 Hem Outer Contour Analysis

In this section, the evaluation focuses on comparing the outer contour of the actual formed hems with the theoretical target outer contour. Each sample outer contour was extracted and analysed to assess how closely the actual hemming results followed the intended target geometry. The attention was given to the overall shape in terms of continuity and homogeneity of the outer hem contour. This comparison provides insights into the dimensional accuracy of the hemming process. Figure 5.9, Figure 5.10 and Figure 5.11 illustrate the comparison of the outer hems contour for samples in experimental series II, experimental series III and experimental series IV respectively.

Figure 5.9 Deviation between the outer contour of the theoretical hem and the outer contour of the actual achieved hems in experimental series II

Figure 5.10 Deviation between the outer contour of the theoretical hem and the outer contour of the actual achieved hems in experimental series III

Figure 5.11 Deviation between the outer contour of the theoretical hem and the outer contour of the actual achieved hems in experimental series IV

The analysis of the hem outer contours revealed that all samples exhibited good overall homogeneity, except for the sample formed using the two stage forming strategy in experimental series IV, which showed noticeable lower homogeneity in the hem outer contour (see Figure 5.11). This again demonstrated the better performance of the single stage forming toolpath over the two stage forming toolpath in terms of reducing wrinkling (see section 5.2) and providing better homogeneity and continuity to the hem outer contour.

The geometric complexity, such as changes in corner radii, also influences the outer contour of the hems, potentially contributing to discontinuities. This was particularly evident at the 20 mm radii in experimental series III samples. Apart from the change in radius, this phenomenon is most likely attributed to the reduced flange length and its interaction with the forming tool or the applied pre-hemming strategy. Additionally, the minor wrinkling identified in section 5.3 likely contributed to these deviations.

The measured deviations were generally ranging around 2.8 mm for samples in experimental series II and IV, and around 2.2 mm for samples in experimental series III, with minimum deviations of 0 mm and maximum deviations of approximately 3.2 mm. This indicates that greater flange lengths resulted in higher deviation values, while shorter flange lengths contributed to lower deviation values.

It is important to note that a measured deviation of 0 mm does not necessarily imply a perfect match with the theoretical outer contour. Instead, it often reflects a condition where the flange length at the corner was insufficient, causing the flange to slip underneath the forming tool. As a result, the material was pushed outward during forming, leading to an outer contour that aligns with the theoretical profile, and often the formation of a visible gap. For example, this behavior was observed in the linear 45° and smooth transition flange relief samples from

experimental series III at the 10 mm corner radius, as illustrated in Figure 4.36 and Figure 4.37.

A roll-in effect was also observed across all samples when comparing the actual hem outer contour with their theoretical hem outer contour. Notably, there appears to be a correlation between flange length and the magnitude of deviation as mentioned previously, manifested by an inward shift in the hem contour. This trend is most likely due to the greater amount of material present in longer flanges. This increases the contact area between the flange and the forming tool, promoting a more pronounced roll-in. Additionally, longer flanges may require a higher number of tool passes during the forming operation, further contributing to the roll-in effect.

6 Summary and Outlook

This study explored the application of ISF for corner hemming, an area not previously investigated in detail. Considering challenges such as wrinkling and geometric inaccuracies that often arise in corner hemming operations, there was a clear motivation to explore corner hemming by means of ISF.

Through a comprehensive experimental setup, a wide range of variables was examined. These included four different corner radii (5 mm, 10 mm, 15 mm, and 20 mm), three flange lengths, five flange relief designs, different material removal surface area values, and different tools and toolpath strategies.

The results confirmed that forming corner hems using ISF is feasible, but under specific conditions. Successful hemming was consistently achieved for 15 mm and 20 mm corner radii, particularly when using flange relief designs such as linear 45° and smooth transition, shorter flange lengths, and a single stage forming strategy. However, the feasibility of ISF for smaller corner radii, such as 5 mm and 10 mm, was notably limited. In these cases, issues such as wrinkling, open corners, and geometric inaccuracy were more frequent.

The longer flange lengths were found to produce wrinkles, especially at smaller corner radii. On the other hand, shorter flange lengths required greater control during pre-hemming and benefited from the use of customized tools. Among the tested strategies, the single stage continuous forming strategy consistently produced better results than the two stage forming strategy, decreasing the occurrence of wrinkles and improving the overall homogeneity of the hem outer contour. This strategy delivered improved geometric accuracy and reduced processing time.

An important correlation was observed between flange length and the achieved corner hem radius. Longer flanges generally led to larger, more accurate radii in the 20 mm corner, while shorter flanges tended to approach the 15 mm corner more closely. However, shorter flanges were also more prone to corner gaps, particularly when combined with flange relief designs that resulted in higher material removal values such as the smooth transition. Although increased material removal value helped reduce wrinkling, it also led to larger gaps in tight radii, especially at 5 mm and 10 mm corners.

Roll-in effects were evident in all samples through comparing the actual hem outer contour with their theoretical hem outer contours. A clear correlation was found between flange length and deviation magnitude, with longer flanges showing more inward deviation. This is likely attributed to the increased contact area between the tool and the material, as well as the higher number of tool passes required, both of which contribute to the pronounced roll-in effect.

From a practical standpoint, the pre-hemming operation using a customized tool proved effective in preparing the flange geometry. The combination of single stage continuous forming with circular and reversible toolpaths yielded the most consistent results. Across the tested flange relief designs, the linear 45° and smooth transition samples achieved the best

results among all other flange relief designs. Therefore, the most recommended forming strategy based on the experimental results consists of flanging with a 20 mm tool using a circular reversible toolpath with lubrication and 1.0 mm step size. And pre-hemming with a customized 10 mm tool applied through a continuous circular toolpath that includes corner forming and a step size of 0.5 mm. In addition, final hemming using the 20 mm tool with a single stage continuous circular reversible toolpath with 0.5 mm step size. The linear 45° and smooth transition flange reliefs are recommended, as they consistently delivered the best results in terms of geometry, homogeneity, and wrinkling reduction.

Despite these promising findings, limitations remain. Corner hemming was clearly more effective at 15 mm and 20 mm radii. Hemming at 10 mm and 5 mm corners presented significant challenges, including open hems, and inconsistent contours. The influence of flange length was also critical as longer flanges increased wrinkling occurrence, while shorter flanges increased the likelihood of gaps at corners.

In addition to these findings, certain process limitations were identified. The two stage forming strategy consistently led to increased wrinkling, particularly around corners. Furthermore, shorter flange lengths especially in combination with high material removal values tended to produce open corners and visible gaps, particularly at the 5 mm and 10 mm radii. This was evident in experimental series III, where reduced flange length led to significant corner gaps. Based on these observations and within the tested process parameters, flange lengths below the values used in series III are not recommended, as they may compromise hem closure at corners.

Looking ahead, several future research directions are recommended. Studies should be extended to include additional materials such as aluminium alloys and high strength steels. Moreover, a comprehensive evaluation of the hem geometry including hem pack size, hem length, hem thickness distribution, and hem edge springback will be beneficial for expanding the applicability of ISF in industrial production. Further investigation into the use of adhesives and sealants could also offer insights into the quality of hemming joints, thereby broadening ISF potential for future manufacturing applications.

Future investigations should also consider repeating the experiments with a modified die design, ideally with a smaller bending radius (e.g. 1-2 mm). This could result in short flanges that are better angled directly after flanging, potentially eliminating the need for a separate pre-hemming stage. Furthermore, future studies could examine variations in the forming tools employed during the hemming process. Specifically, using smaller tools, such as the 10 mm diameter customized tool used for pre-hemming, could provide dual functionality for the pre-hemming and final hemming stages. Alternatively, both operations could be integrated into a single stage toolpath. This approach could simplify the workflow and significantly reduce the overall processing time.

Overall, this study contributes valuable knowledge to the domain of ISF and offers new possibilities for its integration in complex sheet metal hemming tasks, particularly in applications where corner hemming plays a critical structural or aesthetic role.

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